

BRIEF REPORT

Fabrication of hydrogel mini-capsules as carrier systems

[version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]

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Abstract

Conventional drug administration often results in systemic action, thus needing high dosages and leading to potentially pronounced side effects. Targeted delivery, employing carriers like nanoparticles, aims to release drugs at a target site, but only a small fraction of nanoparticles actually reaches it. Microrobots have been proposed to overcome this issue since they can be guided to hard-to-reach sites and locally deliver payloads. To enhance their functionality, we propose microrobots made as deformable capsules with hydrogel shells and aqueous cores, having the potential added advantages of biocompatibility, permeability, and stimulus-responsiveness. In this study, we present a cost-effective method for fabricating core-shell structures without the use of organic solvents or surfactants. The process begins with the dripping of a mixture of hydrogels, agarose and alginate, into a solution to gelate the drops into beads. After they are loaded with calcium ions at different concentrations, they are immersed in an alginate solution to form the shell. Finally, the beads are heated to let the agarose melt and diffuse out, leaving a liquid core. By varying the concentration of calcium ions, we obtain shells of different thickness. To estimate it, we have developed a method using the colour intensity from microscope images. This allowed us to observe that lowering the calcium ions concentration below a threshold does not lead to the formation of continuous shells. For higher concentrations, although the core may remain partially gelled, continuous shells successfully form. Therefore, our fabrication process could find applications in drug delivery, encapsulation systems, and microrobotics.

Plain language summary

Conventional drug administration methods often lead to widespread effects in the body and dosage-related side effects. Targeted drug delivery aims to release drugs precisely where they're needed by

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1. **Mahmut Selman Sakar** , Ecole Polytechnique Federale de Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland
2. **Dr. Sudhir G. Warkar** , Delhi Technological University, Delhi, India

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

using carriers. However, only a few of them actually reach the intended target. To address this issue, scientists are exploring microrobots, tiny machines that can reach places deep inside the body. We design microrobots as soft liquid-filled capsules. In our research, we've developed an affordable method to make these capsules without using harsh chemicals. The obtained capsules have a controllable shell thickness and a liquid or almost liquid core. This makes our capsules promising candidates as microrobot bodies or as drug delivery carriers.

Keywords

alginate, agarose, core-shell, hydrogel capsules, microrobotics

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Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

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1 Introduction

Most routes of drug administration (*e.g.* intravenous) lead to systematic action of the drug, as topical administration is possible only for suitable diseases. In many cases, this requires much higher dosages than those needed if the administration could be topical, resulting in much more significant side effects. This is particularly problematic for chemotherapy. To address this issue, conventional drug delivery approaches aim to improve aqueous solubility and chemical stability of the drug, to increase its pharmacological activity and to reduce side effects while maintaining the therapeutic concentrations at the target site. A suitable approach to reduce drugs' side effects consists in adopting carriers, such as nanoparticles, that could release the drug only at the target site or to target tissues or cells, which is known as targeted drug delivery. Whereas nanoparticles-based targeted drug delivery has proved to enhance the therapeutic index and reduce adverse side effects, there are still open issues related to drugs toxicity, selectivity and dosage. One key problem is that only a tiny fraction of the drug-loaded nanoparticles reaches the target site (*e.g.* a solid tumour)¹.

Microrobots have been proposed to overcome these issues². The main feature of these tiny robotic devices is their controlled navigation, which could allow them to be guided to hard-to-reach target sites inside the human body. Microrobots could thus become a non-invasive approach to topically administer drugs (or drug-loaded carriers) at sites that are not currently suited to topical administration. Although recent advances in microrobotics for drug delivery applications, tracking and guiding microrobots *in vivo* remains challenging, and their ability to move through body tissues and crossing biological barriers is still limited². To make microrobots ultra-deformable and able to move across tissues and barriers, a possible design consists of a thin and soft shell enveloping a liquid core. The microrobots' building materials should be biocompatible or biodegradable. Moreover, the shell should be permeable and possibly stimuli-responsive, to release the cargo in response to specific conditions, while the core should be aqueous, to carry hydrophilic payloads. Therefore, we propose to build microrobots as core-shell capsules^{3,4} having an aqueous liquid core and a biodegradable hydrogel-based shell^{5,6}.

Core-shell and hollow particles can be prepared using a variety of methods^{7,8}, including: Layer-by-Layer (LbL)^{9,10}, sol-gel^{11,12}, solvent evaporation, spray-drying¹³, double emulsions (O/W/O or W/O/W)¹⁴. However, none of these methods is suited to the fabrication of the ultra-deformable microrobots we have devised, which requires mild process conditions to avoid damages to the potential payloads.

In this article, we introduce a method for fabricating core-shell capsules that have a liquid aqueous core and a hydrogel shell, which involves no organic solvents, surfactants, or low/high pHs. We report the characterization of the obtained core-shell capsules, with a focus on the shell thickness and its dependence on the process parameters. In particular, obtaining a thin

yet continuous shell is essential for the capsules to be deformable yet stable. The proposed process holds potential also for the fabrication of micro-capsules and core-shell particles for different applications, including drug-delivery systems other than microrobotics ones.

2 Methods

2.1 Materials

Sodium alginate (CAS 9005-38-3), agarose (CAS 9012-36-6), sodium citrate dihydrate (SCD)(CAS 6132-04-3), calcium chloride (CAS 10043-52-4) and iron (III) oxide nanopowder <50 nm (CAS 1309-37-1) were purchased from Merck. MilliQ water is used unless differently stated (Elix[®] Advantage 10 Water Purification System).

To fabricate the shell we have chosen alginate, a natural polymer which shows attractive properties such as biocompatibility, low cost, ease of gelation, inert nature¹⁵. Alginate undergoes a reversible gelation process when divalent ions (*e.g.* Ca²⁺, Ba²⁺ or Sr²⁺) are added to the polymeric solution and it returns to the original liquid form when exposed to chelating agents that bind the divalent ions with a higher affinity constant¹⁶.

2.2 Preparation of the core-shell particles

The process for preparing the core-shell beads is depicted in [Figure 1](#) and a tutorial video can be found in the Extended Data¹⁷.

1. The agarose-alginate water solution is prepared mixing a 1% w/v agarose solution (previously heated at 95°C to promote dissolution) and a 4% w/v alginate solution to have overall concentrations of 0.5% agarose and 2% alginate. The obtained warm solution is added drop-wise to a CaCl₂ 100 mM solution using a 10 mL syringe (Terumo[®]) to form gel beads because of the immediate crosslinking of alginate by calcium ions. The beads are kept in the CaCl₂ solution for about 10 minutes to complete the crosslinking.
2. The particles are then washed with 100 ml of water to remove the excess of CaCl₂, transferred into a 50 mM solution of sodium citrate dihydrate (SCD) and kept overnight. SCD is meant to chelate Ca²⁺ ions and thus de-crosslink the alginate template, leaving beads of just agarose.
3. The agarose cores are then washed again with water and transferred in CaCl₂ solutions at different concentrations (ranging from 0.1 mM to 100 mM) to obtain different shell thickness.
4. After 1 hour of equilibration in the CaCl₂ solution, the cores are picked up and briefly placed on a filter paper to remove the excess solution from the surface (avoiding the formation of an irregular shell). They are then immersed for 15 minutes in a solution of alginate 0.5% w/v, in which 0.2 mg/ml of 50 nm Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles are suspended, to form a continuous and reddish shell.

- After 15 minutes, the beads are briefly rinsed in water and then transferred in a 100 mM CaCl_2 solution to complete the crosslinking of the alginate shell. To obtain a liquid core, the beads are placed in a thermal bath at a temperature of 90/95°C for 2–7 hours, allowing the agarose to liquefy and diffuse out.

We immersed capsules purposely made using cores loaded with particles (CaCO_3 or SiO_2) in a SCD solution to de-crosslink the shell and assess the core liquidity. The release of the particles from the capsules highlighted that the cores were insubstantial after 6–7 hours of thermal bath, although we still observed a light gel residue (see Extended Data, video “ChargedCapsuleSiO2_core”)¹⁷.

2.3 Capsules characterization

We characterized the capsules using an Hirox digital microscope (Hirox HRX-01) and analysing the images by two different approaches: i) direct measure of the shell thickness – this method is however challenging for thin shells; ii) indirect measure based on shell colour.

We assume the volume of the alginate shell V_s to be proportional to the amount of Ca^{2+} ions in the core (see Figure 2), such that

$$V_s = \alpha n_{\text{Ca}^{2+}} \quad (1)$$

where α is a proportionality constant (to be determined) and $n_{\text{Ca}^{2+}} = V_c [\text{Ca}^{2+}]$ is the number of Ca^{2+} ions moles in the core ($[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$ is assumed to be equal to the concentration of the CaCl_2 solution the cores have been soaked in before forming the alginate shell). Considering that $V_c = \frac{4}{3}\pi R_c^3$ (where R_c is the core radius) and $V_s = \frac{4}{3}\pi[(R_c + h)^3 - R_c^3]$ (where h is the thickness of the shell), we obtain

$$h = R_c \left(\sqrt[3]{\alpha [\text{Ca}^{2+}] + 1} - 1 \right) \quad (2)$$

We thus fabricated batches of capsules by soaking the agarose cores in CaCl_2 solutions at concentrations ranging between 0.1 and 100 mM (0.1, 1, 2, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 50 and 100 mM, three to five samples for each concentration) – see Figure 3. We stained the shell by adding iron oxide nanoparticles

Figure 1. Illustration of the core-shell particles fabrication process. The core-shell beads preparation involves the dripping of an agarose-alginate mixture in a CaCl_2 solution, followed by washing and transferring the beads to a sodium citrate dihydrate (SCD) solution. After loading them with Ca^{2+} ions (by equilibration in CaCl_2 solutions of different concentrations), the beads are placed in an alginate solution containing Fe_2O_3 nanoparticles to form the shell. Subsequently, they are washed and transferred to another CaCl_2 solution to consolidate the shell. By heating the beads, the agarose liquefies and diffuses out, resulting in a liquid core within the shell.

Figure 2. Schematics showing the expected shell thickness increase with the increasing concentration of calcium chloride.

to the alginate solution to enhance its detection and ease the measurement of its thickness (particles were chosen instead of a dye, as most dyes would diffuse away and/or stain the core too).

We first measured the shell thicknesses using the measuring tool of the digital optical microscope's software. To perform a linear fit and obtain an estimate for α , we rearranged Equation 2 to obtain an equation of the form $y = ax$, leading to:

$$\left(\frac{h}{R_c} + 1\right)^3 - 1 = \alpha [\text{Ca}^{2+}] \quad (3)$$

Obtained a value for α , Equation 2 can be used to calculate the expected shell thickness as a function of the CaCl_2 solution concentration. Therefore, we estimated the thickness of the shells too thin to be directly measured by extrapolating values from the fitted curve.

To better estimate the thickness of such thin shells, we have devised a complementary approach based on the assumption that the shell colour intensity (given by the iron oxide nanoparticles) linearly depends on its thickness. To have consistent measurements of the colour intensity, we set and kept fixed the parameters for the microscope images acquisition (illumination, camera settings). The parameters values were chosen to obtain good quality images with all the inspected thicknesses. The image processing develops as follow:

1. each image of the set is segmented creating two clusters: one with all the pixels corresponding to the capsules, and a second one with the background;
2. in each image, a small portion at the centre of the capsule cluster is automatically selected, and the RGB values of the corresponding pixels are extracted;
3. in each image, an average value for each of the three colour channels is calculated over the selected region;

4. in each image, average channel values corresponding to the background are also calculated;
5. from the colour intensities extracted at point 3 and 4, the red channel value, the value of the red channel minus the background, and the value of the red channel minus the blue channel are calculated and related to the CaCl_2 concentration and to the theoretical shell thickness (calculated with Equation 2);
6. a linear fit of the measured shell thickness over the measured R-B colour intensity is performed, obtaining a relation to estimate the shell thickness from the colour intensity.

From this we again extrapolate the expected thickness for the non-measurable shells and compare the predictions with those obtained from Equation 2.

3 Results & discussion

3.1 Characterization of the capsules

The protocol described in section 2.2 led to the successful fabrication of the microcapsules. Figure 3 reports the microscopy images of two representative samples, acquired using transmitted illumination to emphasize the shell and measure its thickness.

First, in Figure 4(a), the data related to the measured thicknesses of the hydrogel capsules are linearized through the leftside of Equation 3 and plotted against CaCl_2 concentration (which equals Ca^{2+} concentration). Fitting the right side of Equation 3 to the linearized thickness data, we found a value of 0.033 mM^{-1} . In Figure 4(b) the comparison between the thickness values predicted by the fitted Equation 3 (orange crosses) and the measured ones (blue dots) is shown to be consistent. The fitted equation also provides a first estimation of the shell thickness for $[\text{CaCl}_2] < 5 \text{ mM}$, for which we could not measure the thickness directly.

Figure 3. Structure of the hydrogel microcapsules: **a)** and **b)** optical microscope images of two capsules of different thicknesses.

As explained in section 2.3, we extracted the average intensity of the red, green and blue components from an area corresponding to the centre of the capsules in the acquired images. Considering the reddish colouring given by iron oxide nanoparticles to the shell, we have chosen the red component, red minus background, and red minus blue colour intensities to be plotted against the concentration of CaCl_2 soaked by the core of each particle (Figure 5(a)).

Figure 5(a) shows that the values obtained as the difference between the red and the blue components (R–B) do not

saturate at high $[\text{CaCl}_2]$, which instead happens in the other two cases. Therefore, we chose the R–B combination as the most reliable to be correlated to the shell thickness. In Figure 5(b), the measured R–B colour intensity is plotted against the theoretical shell thickness calculated by Equation 2. The plot is non-linear, with a threshold for low thickness values. The measured shell thickness values are plotted against the calculated R–B colour intensity, and the linear correlation between these two data was verified and calculated through a linear fit (Figure 5(c), blue dots and orange line). The crosses lying on the left side of the fitting line correspond to the capsules

Figure 4. Dependence of shell thickness on $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$: **a)** Linearized measured shell thickness (blue dots) alongside the linear fit of the data (orange line); **b)** Comparison between measured shell thickness (blue dots) and the thickness estimated using the parameter obtained from the fitting (orange crosses).

Figure 5. Estimation of shell thickness via colour analysis: **a)** Plot of the mean colour intensity in the selected area of each image: values of the red component (R, red dots), the red minus the background (R–bg, green dots), and the red minus the blue component (R–B, blue dots). **b)** Calculated R–B colour intensities and their mean and standard deviation for each concentration of calcium chloride vs the theoretical shell thickness calculated by Equation 2. **c)** Direct linear correlation between measured shell thickness and R–B colour intensity, including thickness predictions for both measured and non-measured sample. For the latter samples, the fitting predicts negative thickness values, which are not possible. **d)** Comparison of normalized shell thickness: measured (blue dots), predicted by Equation 2 (green solid line), and predicted by the R–B colour intensity (orange crosses and dotted line).

for which the shell thickness was not measurable. The linear relation leads to the prediction of negative thickness values, which are obviously not possible, confirming our hypothesis of a threshold behaviour. This means that below a certain core $[\text{CaCl}_2]$ threshold, alginate shells did not form on top of the agarose cores.

Figure 5(d) shows the comparison between the two estimations and the measured thickness as normalized shell thickness vs concentration of CaCl_2 soaked by the core. They are in good agreement, except for the points below 5 mM, for which the R–B colour intensity hints to the absence of a shell, which makes this second method more reliable for detecting the shell thickness rather than a simple linear extrapolation.

All images, data, and analysis scripts can be found in the Underlying Data¹⁸.

4 Conclusion

In this work, we presented a novel method for the fabrication of core-shell capsules using sacrificial agarose cores as a template to obtain alginate shells of different thicknesses. The method allows to obtain capsules of different shell thickness, by soaking the cores in calcium chloride solutions of different concentrations, and liquid or insubstantial cores.

We also developed a method to estimate the thickness of the capsules' shell from microscopy images by measuring the colour intensity. This was especially meant to estimate the shell thickness of capsules with a shell that could not be directly recognized and measured. By these observations, we found that calcium chloride solutions of concentration ≤ 2 mM lead to capsule shells that are discontinuous or not forming at all, whereas we instead expected from Equation 2 to obtain thin shells.

Our fabrication method allows to make capsules with a shell thickness h down to $\sim 0.1 \times R_{\text{core}}$. Therefore, by miniaturizing the sacrificial cores to the tens of microns range, we expect to obtain much thinner yet continuous shells (in the microns range). Such hydrogel microcapsules could then be used for the development of biomedical microrobots, being potentially very deformable, loadable with drugs, carriers or particles, and based on biocompatible and responsive materials.

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Data availability

Underlying data

Zenodo: Fabrication of Hydrogel Mini-Capsules as Carrier Systems - Underlying data. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8413186>¹⁸.

This project contains the following underlying data:

- images (folder containing the set of images used for the data analysis)
- data.csv (measurements acquired with the microscope software: Tag; CaCl_2 concentration; shell thickness; core radius)
- Software_ThicknessAnalysis.jl (Julia script used for analysing the data)
- Functions_ThicknessAnalysis.jl (functions called in the script “Software_ThicknessAnalysis.jl”)
- readme.txt (file with the specifications on contents and used instrument/illumination conditions)

Extended data

Zenodo: Fabrication of Hydrogel Mini-Capsules as Carrier Systems - Extended data. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8413662>¹⁷.

This project contains the following extended data:

- ChargedCapsuleCaCO3.gif (time-lapse of an hydrogel capsule filled with CaCO_3 to show the nature of the core through the release of the particles)
- ChargedCapsuleSiO2.jpg (image of an hydrogel capsule loaded with SiO_2 microparticles)
- ChargedCapsuleSiO2_core.wmv (video of the particle in the picture - “ChargedCapsuleSiO2.jpg” after shell dissolution)
- TutorialBeadsFabrication.mov (video tutorial showing how the fabrication of the core-shell hydrogel capsules is realized)

Data are available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license](#) (CC-BY 4.0).

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Dr. Sudhir G. Warkar

Delhi Technological University, Delhi, India

Comments of Reviewer:

In the paper entitled "Fabrication of hydrogel mini-capsules as carrier systems" the authors proposed the synthesis of microrobots made as deformable capsules with hydrogel shells and aqueous cores, having the potential added advantages of biocompatibility, permeability, and stimulus-responsiveness. The process of forming alginate hydrogel mini capsules proceed through the dripping of the mixture of alginate and agarose into a calcium chloride solution to form crosslinked shell of alginate and agarose core. The cross-linked alginate shell is de-crosslinked by dipping the beads in sodium citrate dihydrate solution.

The scientific quality of the paper is good and the scientific study of the paper is relevant to the academic and scientific community. The paper also has adequate references cited. However, the manuscript needs a few minor changes/clarification on the following observations:

Reviewer has observed the following issues with the manuscript which the authors must address:

1. The manuscript requires more clarity for better understanding and repeatability.
2. Section 2.2, after de-crosslinking the alginate template, agarose beads were left behind which were transferred to CaCl_2 solution of different concentrations to form shells of different thicknesses. Authors should clarify in the paper whether these shells formed on agarose beads are of which material.
3. If both agarose and alginate get crosslinked by Ca^{2+} then why does only alginate get de-crosslinked on immersing in sodium citrate dihydrate.
4. Section 2.2, a more detailed description of step 5 is required- such as before placing the beads at a temperature of 90-95°C, agarose was in which physical state (solid/liquid). What exactly happens at 90-95°C? [In the abstract, authors mentioned 'Finally, the beads are heated to let the agarose melt and diffuse out, leaving a liquid core'.]

5. More explanation is required for the loading and release of CaCO_3 and SiO_2 in the core.
6. The shell thickness of capsules was measured from microscopy images by measuring the colour intensity-whether the results can be validated by other characterization techniques?
7. The insights need to be incorporated in the paper related to how the hydrogel mini capsules developed as biomedical microrobots can be used for controlled navigation, which could allow them to be guided to hard-to-reach target sites inside the human body.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Polymeric hydrogels for drug delivery, agriculture, metal ion sensing, and water enrichment applications.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 24 Sep 2024

Elisa Roberti

1. Thank you for your feedback. Please consider that in addition to the manuscript, we have uploaded a video demonstrating the protocol. We believe that this provides a clearer visualization and a better understanding, and that it enhances repeatability. In addition, we have addressed all reviewers' comments to further making our manuscript and process clear, easy to understand and reproduce.
2. The agarose beads are submerged in calcium chloride solutions of varying concentrations to absorb the solution. When the CaCl_2 -loaded agarose beads are

transferred into a fresh alginate solution (containing iron oxide nanoparticles), the calcium ions diffuse out, immediately crosslinking the alginate around the agarose beads, forming the shell. The shell is thus made of a Ca-alginate hydrogel containing iron oxide nanoparticles.

3. It is worth clarifying that only alginate crosslinks due to the presence of calcium ions, while agarose forms a gel via a physical mechanism when cooled from high temperature to room temperature. We indeed use these different hydrogels, exploiting their distinct gelation mechanisms, exactly to be able to de-crosslink them selectively.
4. Agarose remains in a gel/solid phase at room temperature and liquefies at temperatures above 90°C. To enable the liquefaction of the agarose gel and the diffusion of agarose molecules through the alginate shell, we heat the core-shell particles (with agarose as the core and alginate as the shell) to 90-95°C, ideally resulting in an agarose-free liquid core surrounded by an alginate shell. However, we have observed that agarose does not fully diffuse out as expected.
5. In microrobots fabrication, it can be useful to load not only magnetic nanoparticles, but also microparticles of other kinds. As an example, we tried these two different kinds of particles, with CaCO₃ being also sensitive to acidic pH. SiO₂ microparticles were loaded in the agarose solution before realizing the cores, while CaCO₃ microparticles were nucleated directly in the already-made cores as an alternative loading method, through the reaction of CaCl₂ with Na₂CO₃. The aim of this experiment was to verify the possibility to load or nucleate particles inside the core, as well as to aid the visualization of the final consistency of the core: we thus dissolved the shell and observed how the loaded particles were released to infer whether the core was fully liquid or had the consistency of a very soft gel.
6. The shell thickness was also measured directly with the measuring tool of our digital microscope, for the capsules whose shell was thick enough to be detected. The colour intensity calculation was performed to also extrapolate data for shells that were not directly measurable by optical microscopy. Our results suggest that there is in fact no substantial/continuous shell for low CaCl₂ concentrations.
7. *The "Conclusions" section was revised to address the question.*

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 23 January 2024

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This article introduces a technique to fabricate capsules with an alginate shell and liquid core. The technique is described in detail, accompanied by a video that contains step-by-step descriptions. The shell thickness is measured using optical images. Two methods to estimate the shell thickness are proposed: from the CaCl_2 concentration and from the shell colour intensity. The colour difference is due to the presence of iron oxide nanoparticles. Here are some comments on the rationale behind the design of the capsules and the presentation of the methodology.

1. Authors hypothesize that the ability to move across tissues and barriers requires "ultradeformability". Please provide a technical description of "ultradeformability". How do we measure the deformability of a liquid-filled soft shell? How does this measure depend on shell thickness, mechanical properties of the shell, and the viscosity of the liquid in the core? What is the role of osmotic pressure?
2. What is the desired level of deformability? Where is this specification come from (i.e., the size of the holes in the barrier)? Do we know how deformable the immune cells are as a starting point? Can they penetrate into solid tumour? I brought up solid tumour as this is the case mentioned by the authors in the introduction. If the immune cells cannot, would it be reasonable to believe that an engineered capsule can?
3. As a follow up to the first two comments, what is the liquid inside the capsule? If the liquid inside the capsule is molten, de-polymerized agarose instead of water as intended, would that influence the deformability of the capsule or the release of the cargo?
4. Please substantiate the claim that none of the existing fabrication methods are suited to fabricate core-shell capsules without damaging potential payloads. There are numerous articles on the fabrication of hydrogel-containing core-shell capsules, specifically alginate or chitosan as the shell material. Majority of these articles show encapsulation and release of drugs. What am I missing here?
5. The alginate capsule is permeable and highly deformable. How would the cargo be protected while crossing barriers? How do you envision to implement selective permeability in order to protect the cargo and release at the target location? Is this strategy compatible with the way the capsules are fabricated?
6. I could not find statistics on how many capsules were fabricated, size range, and dispersity. Why do we see few data points on the plots? Considering the throughput of the fabrication method, I would expect to see many measurements per condition (e.g., CaCl_2 concentration) with mean and standard deviation instead of a single data point.
7. Why is the volume of the alginate shell V_s proportional to the amount of Ca^{2+} ions in the core. Please plot shell thickness with respect to capsule size. That would nicely accompany your illustration shown in Figure 2.
8. What is the effect of adding iron oxide nanoparticles into the alginate to the stiffness of the shell? Is this strategy compatible with the overall objective of making "ultradeformable" capsules?

9. The discussion does not address an important issue. What future steps will transform the core-shell capsules described in this work into microrobots? How do you envision to implement the required fabrication steps and control strategies? What are the trade-offs and challenges in terms of material choice and design parameters? For example, if magnetic force is going to be applied to pull these capsules through barriers, magnetic volume must be increased which will inherently constrain the deformability of the shell.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Partly

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Microrobotics, microfabrication, hydrogels, magnetic actuation

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 24 Sep 2024

Elisa Roberti

1. We thank the reviewer for this question, which allows us to better explain the concept of ultra-deformability in the context of micro robotics. In the literature, the term "ultradeformability" is primarily associated with liposomes or transferrinsomes, particularly those used for transdermal delivery. In that specific scenario, there is a requirement for vesicles capable of substantial squeezing to pass through skin pores without losing their cargo (Souto et al., 2021; Sharma et al., 2024). We broadly define "ultra-deformability" as the ability of microrobots/structures to deform substantially under small external forces (same order of magnitude as those needed to drag them through a liquid) and to pass through openings that are smaller than their size (Vorselen et al., 2020)(Simrah et al., 2024). Possible methods to measure

deformability could involve compelling these soft beads to traverse a capillary, nanoindentation, or AFM in force distance curve-based imaging mode. (Vorselen et al., 2020). These techniques are also commonly employed for liposomes or polymersomes. Lowering the thickness and/or elastic modulus of the shell reduces its bending and tensional stiffness, thus increasing the deformability/compliance of the whole structure. The viscosity of the liquid core influences the rate of deformation, as well as the effective deformability of the structure (the lower the viscosity, the lower the forces/stresses required for the liquid to flow within the core). The viscosity can play an additional role if the mechanism of deformation involves a change of volume and flow of the core liquid through the porous shell (the lower the viscosity, the lower the flow resistance). As for the osmotic pressure, its changes can induce swelling or deswelling of the shell and structure, leading to a volume change and change of mechanical properties of the shell. We have thus revised our manuscript to provide an explanation of the concept of ultra-deformability.

2. Leukocytes are sufficiently deformable and elastic to move inside the small capillaries (diameter $< 5 \mu\text{m}$) that reach solid tumors, to travel through the interstitial spaces of tissues ($< 1 \mu\text{m}$), and to extravasate through the nanometric junctions between the endothelial cells of the leaky vasculature in the tumor microenvironment (100 to 500 nm (Wilhelm et al., 2016), depending on the tumor type and stage). Leukocytes can indeed migrate to and infiltrate inside tumors (Wu et al., 2022). If deformable enough, capsules of diameter $\geq 10 \mu\text{m}$ should be able to at least move in small capillaries. By making them smaller or even more deformable, we could potentially enable their extravasation from blood vessels, particularly considering the gaps between endothelial cells in tumor tissue. Nonetheless, here we report a preliminary investigation of a fabrication method potentially useful for preparing ultra-deformable capsules. The assessment of the fabrication method is performed on millimeter-sized capsules to ease the process and analysis, and further effort would be needed to adapt the method to make microcapsules of the size required for the envisioned applications.
3. Our initial assumption was that once the agarose melted, it would easily diffuse out of the shell, leaving a completely liquid aqueous core. However, we realized that although the agarose melts, the core is not fully liquid (see Extended Data). This could negatively affect the deformability of the capsules. Nonetheless, we have chosen the lowest concentration of agarose that allows the formation of a gel in the initial steps of the process, to minimize the amount of residual agarose in the core after its melting and diffusion out of the shell. With this in mind, we assume that the non-complete liquefaction of the core will eventually affect the deformability of the capsule, yet only negligibly. For what concerns the release of the cargo, cargo diffusivity, hydrophilicity and dimensions will have to be taken into account, but we do not expect agarose residues inside the core to make a substantial difference, as deformability and cargo release will mostly depend on the shell properties.
4. We agree that many processes exist to fabricate hydrogel-containing core-shell capsules, e.g. the template-based formation of alginate-chitosan capsules through the layer-by-layer method. However, we have been looking for methods that lead to capsules where both the shell and the core are aqueous, that allow the core to be liquid, and that use only very mild conditions (e.g. \sim neutral pH in all steps, to allow the loading of pH-sensitive cargos). None of the reported fabrication methods, to the

best of our knowledge, have all the features we need for our purposes (e.g. LbL deposition of chitosan requires acidic pH). Therefore, we have conceived this new fabrication process, and we report here a preliminary assessment of the produced capsules, confident that it could complement the various fabrication processes already reported in the literature.

5. Alginate nano and microparticles have been extensively used to obtain optimal drug delivery systems (Hariyadi and Islam, 2020; He et al., 2020; Abourehab et al., 2022), due to some of the properties of this hydrogel such as the low toxicity, chemical versatility, and pH sensitivity. Notably, there are many examples of alginate-based drug delivery systems capable of targeting and releasing cargos under specific conditions, such as at the low acidic environment near tumors (He et al., 2020). Ideal drug-delivery systems are expected to securely encapsulate drugs without leakage, before reaching the target site and release the drugs upon reaching the target. Alginate-based nanoparticles can accumulate at the target site via passive or active targeting, but some strategies are needed to disassemble the capsule or increase permeability, developing stimuli-responsive capsules. In our specific case, the deformability for crossing the barriers is firstly given by the bending of the shell, and in part by its extension/compression, aiming at minimizing the inner volume changes so as to minimize the exchange of liquids between the core and the environment, decreasing the cargo losses while crossing barriers. Moreover, the volume change can be stimuli-induced and used to trigger the cargo release.
6. We realized many samples, then we thoroughly analyzed from 3 to 5 particles per each experimental condition, and considering the high reproducibility of the results, we assumed it to be sufficient. Then considering the samples number, we thought it was more meaningful to report the values of the single samples rather than mean and standard deviation.
7. *The thickness, and thus the volume of the alginate shell is proportional to the amount of Ca^{2+} ions that were previously loaded into the core because it determines the number of cross-link bonding that each bead can realize. Once the core is put in a solution at a fixed alginate concentration, the Ca^{2+} ions will be released, inducing the crosslinking of the alginate in the nearby of the cores, and producing a shell whose thickness will be (at first approximation) determined by the number of Ca^{2+} ions loaded in the core itself (which could be approximated as the product of CaCl_2 concentration times the volume of the core, dealing with a hydrogel which is mostly water).* Nonetheless, the most important parameter that we are changing here is the CaCl_2 concentration, whereas there is no large variation among the core radii, with the small polydispersity observed being due to the fabrication method. Moreover, the simple reported model assumes that the core has constant volume during the process, whereas we observed experimentally that the cores undergo a certain degree of swelling and deswelling during the process, also depending on the concentration of CaCl_2 . For these reasons, we have not included the resulting plot of shell thickness versus capsule core radius as it is not informative and shows no clear correlation in the small range of radii observed.
8. The current amount of nanoparticles used is very low, sufficient only for a clear visualization of the capsules but irrelevant from a deformation standpoint. To obtain magnetic microrobots, much higher concentrations of magnetic nanoparticles (or ferrofluid) will be needed. However, by using nanoparticles with a diameter of less

than 10 nm and potentially placing them in the core instead of the shell, the impact on deformability will be minimized.

9. The "Conclusions" section was revised to address the question.

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